

FLEAS AND THE DISEASES THEY CAUSE. FIGHT FLEAS AND PREVENT THEM

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Annotation: Flea is one of the most common parasites in cats, dogs and other furry pets. In nature, there are such fleas that, even temporarily, in snakes, some fleas parasitize ea hashrarotar larvae. Cats have cat fleas (*Ctenocephalides falis*), dogs have dog fleas (*Ctenocephalides canis*), rats have squid fleas (*Xenopsyllacheopis*) but they can be attacked by humans. Rats and human fleas infect humans with the triggers of plague and sweating sickness. Plague disease is part of the natural-source facultative transmissive disease group. A plague person can be infected by two different ways bian. In the history of mankind, plague plague has caused the inhabitants of the Earth 3 times very large disasters. One of the main ways to avoid fleas is to comply with sanitary and hygienic rules.

Keywords: *Pulex irritans*, *Ctenocephalides canis*, *Xenopsyllacheopis*, *transmissiv*, *justiniana*, *chuma*.

When we talk about fleas, we first bring this creature to the eyes of an infected animal, often the dog is either a cat, constantly scratching in itching. But these animals can infect fleas with human beings. We will talk about fleas in full in this article. Fleas are small ectoparasites, ranging in length from 1 mm to 5 mm. Over the fleas are covered with a hard shiny chitinous cuticle. In the cuticle, there will be chitinous hairs with the tip turned back. Part of the bristles transform to form wide hard teeth. Such teeth would have covered the front and bottom of the head. Feathers, teeth give fleas the opportunity to move freely between the wool and feathers of the master. The thorax has three pairs of legs, and the wings are completely lost in response to adaptation to life through parasitism. It moves

quickly by jumping using its long and muscular hind legs. For example, a human flea can jump to a height of 9 cm, a distance of 32 cm. The abdominal part is made up of 10 joints, and the posterior part houses the genital apparatus. Fleas have a sexual dimorphism: the male is slightly smaller, the last part of the abdominal section becomes recurved upwards. The sexual apparatus of females is made in the form of a sausage-shaped, chitinous reservoir seed-receiving bubble. The female fleas lay up to 400-500 eggs in their lifetime, and the number of eggs in one laying does not exceed 6-10 eggs. Fleas suck blood at least once a day. Because the parasite sucks more blood into the intestine than it sucks, a poorly digested nutrient (blood) protrudes from the anal opening of the insect. Fleas parasitize mainly (95%) in mammals. It is especially parasitic on rodents. They can move from one type of animal to another, not too tightly connected with a particular type of host. Such hematophagous animals are called polyphages. In nature, there are such fleas that, even temporarily, in snakes, some fleas parasitize earthworm larvae. Cats have cat fleas (*Ctenocephalides felis*), dogs have dog fleas (*Ctenocephalides canis*), rats have rat fleas (*Xenopsyllacheopsis*) but they can be attacked by humans.

Human fleas parasitize in humans. The size of the female (*Pulex irritans*) will be 3-4 mm. Human fleas can also live on the body of pets. Fleas are hungry for hot blood, leaving the cooling body of a dead animal and looking for a new host. Rats and human fleas infect humans with the triggers of plague and sweating sickness. When the germs of these severe diseases get into the skin of a person through the excrement of sick people, rats and fleas, they begin to multiply, passing through his scratched area into the blood. Plague disease is part of the natural-source facultative transmissible disease group. Its natural source is rodents, mainly bats, hummingbirds, suckers, and sandflies. A patient with this disease can die in 3-4 days.

The plague can infect a person two different ways:

1. Fleas fed with patient blood also infect themselves with plague triggers (plague jets) along with blood. Plague planes multiply in the stomach and intestines of fleas so much that, as a result, they fill the stomach of the flea, forming a plague stopper that prevents the insect from feeding on normal. When the damaged burg sucks blood, the food goes back to the stomach from the universe, that is, the flea vomits. At this time, plague sticks also fall into the place where fleas "vomit" and injure a person. When stinging areas are smeared, a person can be infected with the plague through scratched skin, that is, through contamination.

2. By mechanical means, such as close contact with the patient, the patient's waste and even air-drop transmission of the plague can occur.

In the history of mankind, plague has caused the inhabitants of the Earth 3 times very large disasters. For the first time in 542, a plague broke out in Egypt and spread to Syria, Asia Minor and Constantinople in a short time, draining the pillow of 10,000 inhabitants every day for 4 months. This epidemic has survived in history under the name "justiniana" Chuma. For the second time, in 1333-4, a new Chuma epidemic is initially occurring in Asia. The disease spreads by various routes (mainly trade caravans) through India, Asia Minor, Constantinople, and later Arabia to Africa and the Mediterranean. In 1348, the population of the Orile of Cyprus was decimated. Within 2-3 years, the disaster would spread throughout the European continent, resulting in a quarter of the European population (25 million) is crushed. Half of the Italian population will be killed.

The disaster is known in history as the Black Death. For the third time, in 1894, chuma began in Hong Kong and spread to almost all Asian countries. 60-90% of the population died from this epidemic. Currently, plague cases are more frequent mainly in the tropic regions of Asia, Africa and South America. Fleas can spread germs of infectious diseases between mammals by sucking their blood not only between humans, but also between rodents, predators, and domestic animals.

One of the main ways to avoid fleas is to comply with sanitary and hygienic rules. It is necessary to keep the moles, places where a person will stay clean, disinfect the floor and bedding in it from time to time with a 2-5% solution of karbol, wash the walls and floor slits with a rag in kerosene wet. In field conditions, chemical drugs against rodents(chlorpicrine, pyrethrum) should be sprayed. Therefore, to combat fleas, it is necessary to spray a 0.05% water emulsion of permethrin, a 0.5% emulsion of carbaphos, a 1% solution of chlorophos on animal skin.

Conclusion; Flea is one of the most common parasites in cats, dogs and other furry pets. To combat fleas, it is always necessary to follow the sanitary and hygienic rule. Fleas cannot live in places with low temperatures and low humidity. Therefore, it is necessary to wash damaged beds with fleas, household household utensils in cold water. Fleas are mostly common in grazing animals. It is less common in animals without permanent habitat. Monkeys that feed on insects do not feed on fleas. Since fleas are very quick-tempered, they can only be seen in the moment when they suck blood.

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